

Kipchumba Biwott_ Data Management Course report

Date: 2022.05.26-27

Topics and structure covered

- i. General Intro to the Course
- ii. Intro and motivation
- iii. Type of the course
- iv. Interactive course/discussions
- v. Importance of sharing own insights
- vi. Hands-on activities/practice
- vii. Small groups – communication, Structure:
- viii. Foundations and File management
- ix. Documentation, sharing and Data Management Plans

During the course we were introduced to data management and gained various knowledge and skills. Information about data management, naming of folders and files, readme files and data directories, various types of data to be collected and kept in folder and file , metadata and Dublin core metadata set and examples. In this course naming of folders and files well was well covered in practical and theoretical session. Data, information and knowledge. The Research Life Cycle, Data management, File management, file formats for long-term access, sharing Data, Storing and archiving data was well covered, this information will be useful in describing the stage and the identifying the cycle of my research project as shown below.

Figure 1. Research cycle

Figure 2. University of Virginia Library Model

Preventing data loss, enabling data sharing, proper use of data, optimal scientific utilization is among information gained, especially by making it findable, accessible, interpretable and reusable to other colleagues.

Information on European infrastructure for biological information such as flat forms, computation, data, tools interoperability, and training. The research data life cycle was elaborate, as we were able to identify the stage in the cycle our project is at and of our colleagues.

Reference managers like Mendeley, Zotero, EndNote, Refworks was covered. Also note taking with Zettelkasten. The importance of note taking such as the unit of experiment: results (data and metadata), figure (visualization) ,a paragraph (textual description with references like method and articles)

Data organisation strategy and the generation of ORCID and DOI identifiers for example the researchgate DOI, and Zenodo DOI. Also we could distinguish data warehouses and data lakes where there is data organization structure in data warehouse

Spreadsheet etiquette, such as not leaving any cells empty, Creating a data dictionary (describe data in the dataset). Putting just one variable in a cell, and importance of not merge cells

Delete pictures on a pen drive and try to recover them using Puran

software:<https://www.lifewire.com/puran-file-recovery-review-2622882> .Data encryption,

Encryption

Deleting file and the meaning of file deleting, main options available such as, data erasure, also known as data clearing, degaussing is another way to remove data, and it disturbs the alignment

of magnetic storage media and physical destruction through shredding, Pulverising or incineration is also an option

Best data authenticity practices, maintaining a single master file of the data. assigning responsibility for master files to a single project team member, regulating write access to master versions of the data files, recording all changes to master files, maintaining all master files in case subsequent versions contain errors., archiving copies of master files at regular intervals, and developing a formal procedure for the destruction of master files, Write-access controls. Careful documentation in relation to any changes made to the master data file. Back it up for long-term access mechanisms and to make data discoverable and citable. Stored Here/Near/Far.

How to store data

Here + Near + Far = 3 copies

Figure 3. Data storage

Data repositories is place where things can be stored and shared for datasets, such as software and protocols. Re3data, general purpose such as DRYAD and Figshare, discipline specific

include image data resource Uniprot Europe nucleotide archive. Making of data management plan using DMPonline during practical session was also covered.

Data Management Plan for the submission of FOREFRONT (KKP_22) proposals

Title and identification number of the proposal

Cytometry of Tcells
27052022

Principal investigator / Host institution

Dr.Bacso Zsolt
University of Debrecen

Scheduled starting date and conclusion of the project

Project intends to start on June 2022 and end September 2024

Are research data being produced during the course of the project?

Yes

Who is responsible for the management of research data? (Contact details, if not a member of the project team)

Biwott Kipchumba

Please describe the type/nature of the data being produced during the course of the project.

Images, Tabular data (Excel and, csv), documentation in lab notebooks, antibodies, proteins, animal (mice) Protocols, Code / software, flourophore. Media to be used, culture cells

Please describe the procedure of the data collection.

Flow cytometry analysis for fluorescence intensities, Microscopy analysis for raw image data

Please describe where and how the data, documentation and the codes will be stored during the course of the project.

It will be stored full backup, incremental backup
it's best to store them on a computer that's not connected to any network

Please describe where and how the data, documentation and the codes will be stored after the course of the project.

It will be stored pen drive, computers and in repositories such as Zenodo database
And University of Debrecen database

Please describe the accessibility of the research data.

Data is accessible via repositories, re3data.org such as institutional, ddiscipline-specific and general
Open access and generates persistent IDs will be consired

Which research data of the project will be of open access?

Images, Tabular data (Excel and, csv), documentation in lab notebooks, antibodies, proteins, animal (mice) Protocols, Code /

	software, flourophore. Media to be used, culture cells
Is there any reason or necessity to restrict the accessibility of the research data?	Data is important to be accessible to avoid duplication
Do you use any standard metadata? (DublinCore, Datacite, etc.)	Yes, Date, location, identifier,Orchid ID
Please describe where and how the metadata will be stored during the course of the project.	Repositories Zenodo Figshare Uniprot ENA
Please describe how the metadata will be accessible?	Metadata will be available in the repositories
Do you use standard or unique identifiers? (DOI, ORCID)	Standard ORCHID identifier Unique DOI
Please describe where and how the metadata, documentation and the codes will be stored after the course of the project.	It will be stored in repositories, such as Zenodo Figshare Uniprot ENA

Does the handling of research data comply with the GDPR regulations?

yes
